

Definition of cross product

The cross product is a specifically 3D function that

- inputs two vectors \vec{k} and \vec{v}
- outputs one vector $\vec{k} \times \vec{v}$

For simplicity, first derive the matrix for a unit vector \hat{k}

- If $\vec{v} \parallel \hat{k}$, then $\hat{k} \times \vec{v} = \vec{0}$

↓

the rest of the derivation assumes that \vec{v} and \hat{k} are non-collinear

We define $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$ as a composition of transformations

Matrix $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$ performs the following actions:

- removes the component of \vec{v} parallel to \hat{k}
- expresses the remaining component of \vec{v} in \mathbb{R}^2
 - rotates that component by 90°
 - re-embeds the result back in \mathbb{R}^3

The resulting vector $([\hat{k}]_{\times}) \vec{v}$ has the following properties:

- $(([\hat{k}]_{\times}) \vec{v}) \cdot \hat{k} = 0$
- $(([\hat{k}]_{\times}) \vec{v}) \cdot \vec{v} = 0$
- $|\hat{k} \times \vec{v}| = |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta)$

where θ is the angle between \hat{k} and \vec{v}

- the 90° rotation is chosen so that

$$\det([\hat{k} \times \vec{v} \mid \hat{k} \mid \vec{v}]) > 0$$

$[\hat{k}]_{\times}$: cross product matrix for unit vector \hat{k}

Matrix $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$ is a composition of the following transformations:

①

removes the projection of \vec{v} onto \hat{k} , computed as $\hat{k} \hat{k}^T \vec{v}$

\leftrightarrow

projects \vec{v} onto plane orthogonal to \hat{k} as

$$(I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T) \vec{v}$$

If we describe the plane by orthonormal matrix $Q = [\hat{q}_1 \mid \hat{q}_2]$

and use the orthogonal projection formula,

$Q Q^T$ becomes the matrix of projection onto the plane

$$Q (Q^T Q)^{-1} Q^T = Q Q^T$$

with geometric actions identical to $I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T$:

$$I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T = Q Q^T$$

Image below shows

- \hat{k}
- \vec{v}
- $\vec{v}_{\parallel} = \hat{k} \hat{k}^T \vec{v}$
- $\vec{v}_{\perp} = (I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T) \vec{v}$

If $\vec{v}_{\perp} = \vec{0}$, then \vec{v} is parallel to \hat{k} ,
and the construction gives $[\hat{k}]_{\times} \vec{v} = \vec{0}$.

For $\vec{v}_{\perp} \neq \vec{0}$, choose

$$\bullet \hat{q}_1 = \frac{\vec{v}_{\perp}}{|\vec{v}_{\perp}|}$$

- $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_2$, computed from $\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_1 \\ \hat{\mathbf{k}} \end{bmatrix} \vec{\mathbf{q}} = \vec{\mathbf{0}}$

the system has

- 2 linearly independent rows $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1$ & $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$
- 3 variables

↓

- solution set is a line in \mathbb{R}^3

- $\vec{\mathbf{q}}$ sign is chosen so that $\det([\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1 \mid \vec{\mathbf{q}} \mid \hat{\mathbf{k}}]) > 0$

- $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_2$ is normalized: $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_2 = \frac{\vec{\mathbf{q}}}{|\vec{\mathbf{q}}|}$

This unique determination of $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_2$ from $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is specific to \mathbb{R}^3

②

expresses vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 coordinates in the basis (\hat{q}_1, \hat{q}_2)

by left-multiplying by $Q^T = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1^T \\ \hat{q}_2^T \end{bmatrix}$

③

applies the 90° rotation: $J = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$

④

returns to standard basis: $Q = \left[\hat{q}_1 \mid \hat{q}_2 \right]$

$$(I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T) = Q Q^T$$

↓

$$[\hat{k}]_{\times} = Q J Q^T (I - \hat{k} \hat{k}^T) = \\ Q J (Q^T Q) Q^T = Q J Q^T$$

$$Q J = \left[\hat{q}_1 \mid \hat{q}_2 \right] \left[\begin{array}{c|c} 0 & -1 \\ \hline 1 & 0 \end{array} \right] = \left[\hat{q}_2 \mid -\hat{q}_1 \right]$$

$$[\hat{k}]_{\times} = (Q J) Q^T = \left[\hat{q}_2 \mid -\hat{q}_1 \right] \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1^T \\ \hat{q}_2^T \end{bmatrix} = \hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T$$

The algebraic manipulations shown below confirm expected geometric actions of $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$

$$\bullet [\hat{k}]_{\times} \hat{k} = (\hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T) \hat{k} = \\ \hat{q}_2 (\hat{q}_1^T \hat{k}) - \hat{q}_1 (\hat{q}_2^T \hat{k}) = \vec{0} \\ \leftrightarrow \\ \text{maps } \hat{k} \text{ to } \vec{0}$$

$$\bullet [\hat{k}]_{\times} \hat{q}_1 = (\hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T) \hat{q}_1 = \\ \hat{q}_2 (\hat{q}_1^T \hat{q}_1) - \hat{q}_1 (\hat{q}_2^T \hat{q}_1) = \\ \hat{q}_2 - 0 \hat{q}_1 = \hat{q}_2 \\ \leftrightarrow \\ \text{rotates } \hat{q}_1 \rightarrow \hat{q}_2$$

$$\bullet [\hat{k}]_{\times} \hat{q}_2 = (\hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T) \hat{q}_2 = \\ \hat{q}_2 (\hat{q}_1^T \hat{q}_2) - \hat{q}_1 (\hat{q}_2^T \hat{q}_2) = \\ \hat{q}_2 0 - \hat{q}_1 = -\hat{q}_1 \\ \leftrightarrow \\ \text{rotates } \hat{q}_2 \rightarrow -\hat{q}_1$$

Since $\hat{q}_1, \hat{q}_2,$ and \hat{k} form a basis of \mathbb{R}^3 ,
 these identities uniquely determine the linear transformation $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$

Expanding the outer products difference gives:

$$\hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & q_{12} \times q_{21} - q_{11} \times q_{22} & q_{12} \times q_{31} - q_{11} \times q_{32} \\ q_{22} \times q_{11} - q_{21} \times q_{12} & 0 & q_{22} \times q_{31} - q_{21} \times q_{32} \\ q_{32} \times q_{11} - q_{31} \times q_{12} & q_{32} \times q_{21} - q_{31} \times q_{22} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note the particular form of the matrix, called skew-symmetric

where $[\hat{k}]_{\times i,j} = -[\hat{k}]_{\times j,i}$ for $i \neq j$

On the next page we will derive
 the unique matrix that satisfies all the geometric properties
 independent of choice of \hat{q}_1 & \hat{q}_2

Computing entries of $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$

As was shown above, $[\hat{k}]_{\times}$ has a skew-symmetric form:

$$\hat{q}_2 \hat{q}_1^T - \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & q_{12} \times q_{21} - q_{11} \times q_{22} & q_{12} \times q_{31} - q_{11} \times q_{32} \\ q_{22} \times q_{11} - q_{21} \times q_{12} & 0 & q_{22} \times q_{31} - q_{21} \times q_{32} \\ q_{32} \times q_{11} - q_{31} \times q_{12} & q_{32} \times q_{21} - q_{31} \times q_{22} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The above matrix can be re-written as $([\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times}) =$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -c & b \\ c & 0 & -a \\ -b & a & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Geometric action of $[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times}$:

$$([\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times}) \hat{\mathbf{k}} = \vec{0}$$

↓

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -c & b \\ c & 0 & -a \\ -b & a & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \\ k_2 \\ k_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This means:

- $-c k_2 + b k_3 = 0$
- $c k_1 - a k_3 = 0$
- $-b k_1 + a k_2 = 0$

Now re-write it so that a, b, c are the unknowns:

(this is where the three independent entries of the 3×3 skew-symmetric matrix can be identified as one vector in \mathbb{R}^3)

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -k_3 & k_2 \\ k_3 & 0 & -k_1 \\ -k_2 & k_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Assuming $k_3 \neq 0$, solving the system produces

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \left[\begin{array}{ccc|c} k_3 & 0 & -k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_3 & k_2 & 0 \\ -k_2 & k_1 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{ccc|c} k_3 & 0 & -k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_3 & k_2 & 0 \\ 0 & k_1 k_3 & -k_1 k_2 & 0 \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{ccc|c} k_3 & 0 & -k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_3 & k_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right] \rightarrow \left[\begin{array}{ccc|c} 1 & 0 & -\frac{k_1}{k_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\frac{k_2}{k_3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right]
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = d \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \\ k_2 \\ k_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

If $k_3 = 0$, pivot using k_2 instead
 If $k_3 = 0$ and $k_2 = 0$, then $\vec{k} = (k_1, 0, 0)$

↓

The system gives $b = 0$ and $c = 0$, so $(a, b, c) = t(k_1, 0, 0)$

Now find the scalar t

The matrix must satisfy

- $([\hat{k}] \times) \hat{q}_1 = \hat{q}_2$
- $([\hat{k}] \times) \hat{q}_2 = -\hat{q}_1$

Use the simple case in \mathbb{R}^3 where

- $\vec{e}_3 = \hat{k}$
- $\vec{e}_1 = \hat{q}_1$
- $\vec{e}_2 = \hat{q}_2$

Then the skew-symmetric matrix becomes

$$[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times} = t \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Apply it to \vec{e}_1 :

$$t \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This is true only when $t = 1$

↓

$$[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times} = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -k_3 & k_2 \\ k_3 & 0 & -k_1 \\ -k_2 & k_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Length of $[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times} \vec{v}$

For unit $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$,
 $[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_{\times} = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T$

$$\hat{k} \times \vec{v} = [\hat{k}] \times \vec{v} = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}$$

$$\vec{v} = \vec{v}_{\parallel} + \vec{v}_{\perp}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v} &= (\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T) (\vec{v}_{\parallel} + \vec{v}_{\perp}) = \\ &= \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} (\mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\parallel} + \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}) = \\ &= \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} (\vec{0} + \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}) = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp} \end{aligned}$$

(a)

$$\bullet \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1^T \\ \hat{q}_2^T \end{bmatrix} \vec{v}_{\perp} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1^T \vec{v}_{\perp} \\ \hat{q}_2^T \vec{v}_{\perp} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |\vec{v}_{\perp}| \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

• \hat{q}_1 is chosen as colinear with \vec{v}_{\perp}

• $|\hat{q}_1| = 1$ and $\hat{q}_2 \perp \vec{v}_{\perp}$

↓

$$|\mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}| = |\vec{v}_{\perp}|$$

(b)

J is a rotation matrix with orthonormal columns

↓

$$|\mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}| = |\mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}|$$

(c)

if $\vec{w} = \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_{\perp}$ (2×1)

$$\bullet \mathbf{Q} \vec{w} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1 & \hat{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}_1 w_1 + \hat{q}_2 w_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

↓

$$|\mathbf{Q} \vec{w}| = |\vec{w}|$$

Combining (a), (b), and (c):

$$\begin{aligned} |\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \vec{v}| &= |\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}| \\ &= |\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_\perp| = |\mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_\perp| \\ &= |\mathbf{Q}^T \vec{v}_\perp| = |\vec{v}_\perp| \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for unit $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$,

$$|\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \vec{v}| = |\vec{v}_\perp|$$

If θ is the angle between $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ and \vec{v} ,

$$|\vec{v}_\perp| = |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta)$$

↓

$$|\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \vec{v}| = |\hat{\mathbf{k}}| |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta) = |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta)$$

Consequences of the $[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_\times$ derivation

From the previous derivation,

$$[\hat{\mathbf{k}}]_\times = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{Q}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -k_3 & k_2 \\ k_3 & 0 & -k_1 \\ -k_2 & k_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

① Off-diagonal entries are 2×2 minors

If $Q J Q^T$ is expanded directly,
the off-diagonal entries first appear as 2×2 minor expressions

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & q_{12} \times q_{21} - q_{11} \times q_{22} & q_{12} \times q_{31} - q_{11} \times q_{32} \\ q_{22} \times q_{11} - q_{21} \times q_{12} & 0 & q_{22} \times q_{31} - q_{21} \times q_{32} \\ q_{32} \times q_{11} - q_{31} \times q_{12} & q_{32} \times q_{21} - q_{31} \times q_{22} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

② Determinant consequence

$$\text{If } \vec{w} = \vec{k} \times \vec{v},$$

\vec{w} is perpendicular to \vec{k} and \vec{v}

Also, length of cross product was derived as

$$|\vec{w}| = |\vec{k}| |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta)$$

This is the area of the parallelogram spanned by \vec{k} and \vec{v} .

So in the parallelepiped with base vectors \vec{k} , \vec{v} and height vector \vec{w} :

- base area = $|\vec{w}|$

- height = $|\vec{w}|$

$$\det([\vec{w} | \vec{k} | \vec{v}]) = \text{base area} \times \text{height} =$$

$$|\vec{w}| \cdot |\vec{w}| = |\vec{w}|^2 = |\vec{k} \times \vec{v}|^2$$

The determinant is positive because $\vec{k} \times \vec{v}$ was chosen so that
($\vec{k} \times \vec{v}$, \vec{k} , \vec{v}) is positively oriented.

$[\vec{j}]_{\times}$: cross product matrix for non-unit vector \vec{j}

Cross product is equivalent to left-multiplication by $[\vec{j}]_{\times}$

$$\vec{j} \times \vec{v} = [\vec{j}]_{\times} \vec{v}$$

For a unit vector \hat{k} : $[\hat{k}]_{\times} =$

0	$-k_3$	k_2
k_3	0	$-k_1$
$-k_2$	k_1	0

Now let \vec{j} be a non-unit vector in the same direction:

$$\vec{j} = |\vec{j}| \hat{k}$$

The cross product length definition gives

$$|\vec{j} \times \vec{v}| = |\vec{j}| |\vec{v}| \sin(\theta)$$

So compared with $\hat{k} \times \vec{v}$,
the direction is the same,
but the length is multiplied by $|\vec{j}|$:

$$\vec{j} \times \vec{v} = |\vec{j}| (\hat{k} \times \vec{v})$$

Therefore,

$$[\vec{j}]_{\times} \vec{v} = |\vec{j}| [\hat{k}]_{\times} \vec{v}$$

so

$$[\vec{j}]^\times = |\vec{j}| [\hat{k}]^\times$$

Since $\vec{j} = |\vec{j}| \hat{k}$,

$[\vec{j}]^\times$ is composed of the same entries of \vec{j} :

$$[\vec{j}]^\times = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -j_3 & j_2 \\ j_3 & 0 & -j_1 \\ -j_2 & j_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Connection with cross-product determinant mnemonic

The commonly taught memorization method is not an ordinary matrix or determinant:

- the first row contains standard basis vectors
- the other rows contain scalar components of \vec{a} and \vec{b}

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = \text{'det'} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{e}_1 & \hat{e}_2 & \hat{e}_3 \\ a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ b_1 & b_2 & b_3 \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

will denote

$$C1 = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} a_2 & a_3 \\ \hline b_2 & b_3 \end{array} \right] \quad C2 = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} a_1 & a_3 \\ \hline b_1 & b_3 \end{array} \right] \quad C3 = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} a_1 & a_2 \\ \hline b_1 & b_2 \end{array} \right]$$

$\vec{a} \times \vec{b}$ is read as symbolic 'cofactor expansion':

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = \hat{e}_1 \det(C1) - \hat{e}_2 \det(C2) + \hat{e}_3 \det(C3) =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \det(C1) \\ -\det(C2) \\ \det(C3) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_2 b_3 - a_3 b_2 \\ a_1 b_3 - a_3 b_1 \\ a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{Since } [\vec{a}] \times = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_3 & a_2 \\ a_3 & 0 & -a_1 \\ -a_2 & a_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_3 & a_2 \\ a_3 & 0 & -a_1 \\ -a_2 & a_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -a_3 b_2 + a_2 b_3 \\ a_3 b_1 - a_1 b_3 \\ -a_2 b_1 + a_1 b_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

